

The Horizon 2020 project GEOFIT looks back at its achievements despite the pandemic in its 3rd year! Involving 24 partners from 10 European countries, GEOFIT is dedicated to developing innovative enhanced geothermal systems, specifically designed for geothermal based retrofitting.

The GEOFIT partnership considers that the implementation of a global, effective, energy-efficient retrofitting strategy for the stock of existing buildings in Europe, will boost the adoption of appropriate geothermal based energy-efficient building retrofitting technologies and methods. Our holistic approach uses the most innovative methods and tools and is being demonstrated in different climate and soil conditions across Europe.

Hello 2022!

Before getting started with the new year, let's take a look at what our project has been doing!

Our main objective for this past year was to finish the designs and start installing the Geofit systems at our demo sites. And we did it! Drilling and excavation works have been completed at four out of five demo sites (Perugia, Aran, Bordeaux and Sant Cugat) and also the installation of the heat pumps. The Geofit system is already running in our demo site in Italy, while the control system for Sant Cugat, the whole installation in Bordeaux, and the retrofitting works in Aran are ready, giving way to the commissioning stages which will kick-off this 2022.

PROJECT NEWS

GEOFIT PROJECT 8TH GENERAL ASSEMBLY IN PERUGIA!

After two years of Covid19, the Consortium met again with a pilot completely finished and the project in its last run. Besides the project progress at technology level, there was special focus on the pilots and their progress. Drilling works at Bordeaux pilot site are finished and the installation of the geothermal system is planned to be done before Christmas, and the control system for the Sant Cugat pilot will be ready by the end of the year. The Consortium took the opportunity to visit the first demo site completed in Sant'Appollinare.

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MODEL DEVELOPMENT AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF NOVEL SHALLOW GROUND HEAT EXCHANGERS

Learn more about the toolkit being designed by GROENHOLLAND which provides design methodologies for vertical borehole heat exchangers, shallow horizontal and slinky type heat exchangers, and earth basket (spiral) heat exchangers.

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ENDING MAY WITH THE 7TH GENERAL ASSEMBLY

Still under a virtual format, the Consortium held its 7th Geofit General Assembly on 20 & 21 May 2021. After presenting the progress made with the core technologies and different progress made with the shallow ground heat exchangers, heat pumps, system integration and efficient management, we celebrated the commissioning of our first pilot site in Perugia and the start of the excavation works at Bordeaux pilot, both important milestones for the project!

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NOVEL PARTICLE-BASED DRILL MODELLING BY LTU

Our partner LTU has introduced a novel particle-based finite element method for modelling the drilling and excavation process, aiming to assist operators in choosing optimum drilling parameters and tools to reduce wear. These simulations will be validated by comparing the outcome with the data from some of the Geofit pilots in the final stage of the project.

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MARCO CALDERONI ELECTED AS NEW CHAIR OF THE RHC-ETIP

Our project coordinator, Marco Calderoni, was elected as new chair of the RHC-ETIP, the European Technology and Innovation Platform on Renewable Heating and Cooling. His mandate has run throughout the whole year.

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DEMO SITES

WORKS IN ARAN PILOT SITE START!

Finally, and after several problems encountered, the Geofit project landed on the Aran Islands and the residential retrofitting works started. The Spanish drilling company Catalana de Perforacions drilled a 100-m deep borehole, and the existing radiators are being partially replaced by low temperature underfloor heating systems in order to improve the efficiency of the heat pump installed.

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STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING IN THE DRILLING PHASE

After performing the structural monitoring at Sant Cugat pilot in summer 2020, SIART shows some of the results on the identification of the vibration propagation across the soil and the building signature (the building own frequencies) obtained during the drilling.

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COMPLETION OF CIVIL WORKS AT PERUGIA

Once the installation of the slinky ground heat exchangers was completed in January 2021, GROENHOLLAND was at the Perugia pilot site to install the fiber optic cable monitoring. Civil works were completed on January 28th, paving the way to the next steps to complete the whole installation and move forward to the commissioning.

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PUBLICATIONS & CONFERENCES

GEOFIT at the World Geothermal Congress 2020+1

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Paper "A Statistical DEM Approach for Modelling Heterogeneous Brittle Materials" (Computational Particle Mechanics, Springer, 2021)

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Thesis "Towards Discrete Element Modelling of Rock Drilling" (Luleå University of Technology, Department of Engineering Sciences and Mathematics, Mechanics of Solid Materials)

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Paper "Design of a Gas-driven Hybrid Adsorption Heat Pump Coupled to Geothermal Heat Exchangers for Retrofitting Applications" (13th IEA Heat Pump Conference, 16-29 April 2021, Jeju, Korea)

Paper "Mid-term Performance Simulation of a Dual Source Heat Pump" (34th ECOS Conference 2021, 28 June - 2 July 2021, Taormina, Italy)

Paper "Deployment of novel geothermal systems, technologies and tools for efficient building retrofitting" (IGW 2021 - ITB International Geothermal Workshop)

Abstract "Development and Validation of Analytical Solutions for Earth Basket (spiral) Heat Exchangers" accepted for the EGC 2022 Congress.

Abstract "GeoFit: Experimental Investigations and Numerical Validation of Shallow Spiral Collectors as a Basis for Development of a Design Tool for Geothermal Retrofitting of Existing Buildings" accepted for the EGC 2022 Congress.

Abstract "Efficient environmental approach of an enhanced geothermal system for energy efficient building retrofitting in a decentralized context" accepted for the EGC 2022 Congress.

Abstract "Discrete Element Modelling of Rock Drilling" accepted for the EGC 2022 Congress.

MEET OUR PARTNERS!

If you are new to our project, this is the place to start! Watch these short interviews and learn in their own words who they are and their role within GEOFIT!

OCHSNER

Ochsner Wärmepumpen (OCHSNER) was founded in 1978 as one of the first companies in Europe producing heat pumps on an industrial scale, being a well-known producer of innovative heat pump systems covering all types of heat sources and capacities ranging from 2 to 1,600 kW.

[▶ WATCH NOW](#)

FAHRENHEIT

FAHRENHEIT was founded in 2002, as a spin-off company of Fraunhofer Institute of Solar Energy Systems (ISE), it is the pioneering company in small capacity adsorption chillers, holding 22 national and international patent families on thermal refrigeration and technological solutions utilizing solid sorbents like silica gel and zeolite.

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KTH & UPONOR

KTH Royal Institute of Technology in Stockholm has become one of Europe's leading technical and engineering universities, as well as a key center of intellectual talent and innovation. KTH is Sweden's largest technical research and learning institution dedicated to advancing knowledge. Uponor is a leading international supplier of plumbing, heating, and cooling systems for the residential and commercial building markets. In Europe, Uponor is also a prominent regional supplier of municipal infrastructure pipe systems.

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GROENHOLLAND

Groenholland Geo-energy systems is a company providing consulting services with regard to the design of shallow geothermal energy systems, site characterization, and building systems simulations. Groenholland furthermore develops, builds, installs, and maintains turn-key ground source energy systems.

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IDP

IDP Ingeniería y Arquitectura Iberia S.L.U. is an innovative and multidisciplinary SME with services ranging from civil & infrastructure engineering, environmental sciences, ICT to project management & consultancy.

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MORE VIDEOS

PROJECT PRESENTATION

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GEOFIT: NOVEL PARTICLE-BASED DRILL MODELLING BY LTU

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WOMEN IN GEOTHERMAL

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Consortium partners

Coordinator: R2M

